

THE USE OF THE METHODOLOGY FOR THE FORMATION OF NATIONAL VALUES IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING STUDENTS THE SUBJECT OF "UPBRINGING".

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14033071>

Annotation: In this context, in the process of teaching "Education" subject, on May 28, 2012, the government decided to "Measures for the further improvement of the system of training of qualified pedagogues and the provision of such personnel to secondary special and vocational education institutions" "On" was adopted, in this decision "In-depth and comprehensive study of foreign experiences in the use of advanced pedagogical methods and technologies, information and communication technologies, electronic educational resources and multimedia presentations in the educational process issue" was defined as a priority task. It is known that pedagogical technology is considered a necessary part of the educational process, and it has been proven in practice that a radical change in the field of education will occur through its use. In our country, the application of pedagogical technologies to the educational process, the reform of the continuous education system, the formation of high professional culture, creative and social activity, and the ability to independently participate in the socio-political life of future professionals are important practical tasks. held.

Key words: pedagogical, creative, creative, deep, action, interactive, activity, site, methodical, result, independent.

During the years of independence, there was a wide opportunity to explore the roots of our spirituality, our values and history. Teaching our national values to younger generations, developing different methods of teaching is one of the main issues of pedagogical science. In pedagogy, interactive methods of teaching are of particular importance. As a result of the use of interactive techniques, interaction, movement, interaction, active communication of the student and the teacher are organized. The main purpose of this method is to create conditions for active, free thinking of the learner by creating the most favorable conditions for the educational process.

When interactive teaching methods are used, cognitive and communicative activities of participants in the educational process are formed. Students will

have the opportunity to understand and think about what they know and think. When interactive methods are used in classes, the task of the teacher will consist in directing the activities of students to achieve the goals of the lesson.

This process demonstrates the intellectual potential, capabilities of the student and increases the quality and effectiveness of training. When organizing a lesson based on an interactive teaching method, not a single student will be left out, that is, they will have the opportunity to openly express what they see, know, think. The main purpose of the interactive method is: to teach learners to think freely, independently, critically, analytically, logically, creatively and make the right decisions on their basis, to learn learners to get out of problem situations without difficulty, to manage to perform theoretical and practical and life tasks, to motivate students to think, to direct them to search and creativity, to encourage The main tools for using interactive techniques are: didactic games, role – playing games, computer games, interactive educational literature, information and communication technologies, methodological exhibitions, etc. Interactive methods encourage students to be active, increase their interest. The active participation of each student in the training is ensured, the opportunity to control and evaluate each student appears. One of the interactive teaching methods is the case-Stade method. This method has practical content and is devoted to methods and means of solving various situational issues and problem situations.

The exact situation described in the case-stadi method links learning to reality: it allows you to analyze the situation in solving the problem, formulate assumptions, identify problems, collect additional information, clarify assumptions and design specific steps. When using the keys-stadi method in the educational process, students develop skills to consolidate knowledge on the topic studied, analyze problems and make decisions individually and Grouply, develop creative and learning abilities, logical thinking, speech and adaptation to environmental conditions, prepare for independent decision-making, such important qualities as responsibility, independence, communicativeness and empathy, self-examination of the formation of reflection, In order to effectively use the Keys-stadi method in the educational process, it is recommended to organize training at the following stages:

Stages	Recommendations
1. Introduction to Keys information supply.	First of all, familiarize yourself with the keys: to get acquainted with the current information supply of the keys in order to have a complete picture of the goals, rules and analysis of the current situation, assessment criteria, information about the keys and on it. Do not rush to analyze the situation during acquaintance with the information supply.
2. Acquaintance with the situation.	Once again, read the information carefully. Mark the lines that are important to you. List the evidence given in the situation description and determine what is known and what needs to be clarified.
3. Identification of the main problem and minor problems.	Try to describe the situation. Determine the essence and the bicyclic. What is the main problem? What other problems can you indicate in the situation presented? Formulate conclusions-identify the main problem and minor problems that are painted on it.
4. Problem analysis.	Mark all the facts related to this problem, not everything in the situation directly depends on it. Answer the question: is it possible to solve it in these conditions? Determine to what extent the problem can be solved?
5. Under consideration the situation is strong and analysis of weak sides.	Organize a SWOT analysis.
6. Alternative decisions formation.	Write down all the solutions to the problem that can be taken in this case. What moral, legal and spiritual difficulties arise in solving the identified problem? Achieve the widest possible application of the educational materials mentioned in the formulation, analysis and selection of alternatives.
7. Proposed alternatives assessment, analysis make and choose.	Prepare to provide information using pinboard or other techniques.
8. Review of practical situations, conclusions decisions on preparation.	Develop a list of practical measures to implement your decision.
9. Preparation of the presentation.	The results of the work can be submitted in writing or verbally if on behalf of the team.
10. Analysis performed presentation of results.	Use presentation women.
11. With the participation of the teacher discussion of performances made and transferred end the analysis.	Pay attention to the main problem.

In the case-stadi method, the situation description and information supply can be of different sizes, in the description of the situations proposed for analysis, the level of detail can also be different, and the level of information abundance can also be data unrelated to analysis. Do not get lost in the fear of the information proposed in the case-stadi method, mark the most necessary

among them, do not consider the situation in a narrow perspective, the problem may suddenly become smaller or disappear altogether. Formulate the action plan after the analysis of the situation is completed and the problem is identified.

Working with the keys in the teaching of the subject" upbringing " has its own characteristics and envisions various technological approaches. The method of creating specific problem situations and the organization of independent work of students depends on the level of complexity of the educational material, the allotted time, the exact contingent of students and a number of other factors.

When teaching" discipline", the following options for organizing classes using keys can be used:

1.The situation is prepared from the beginning by the teacher, and then the part consisting of the incident is read, after the process of asking questions by students is completed, each small group makes its own decision. After that, in an open discussion, its right or wrong sides are discussed.

2.The teacher conducts explanatory work on the technology of analyzing situations for students. Then the groups are given 15-20 minutes. Each small group develops themselves during this time a variant of the situation (from the book, from practical activities). After the development of situations in all communities, the process of collecting information begins: event; questions and answers; decisions made; solution and presentation of its analysis by the authors of the situation. The other team then moves in that sequence.

It is advisable to distinguish the following possibilities of organizing training:

1) each request of additional information is discussed by the readers and the necessary issues are solved to decide on its based solution;

2) requests of each small group of students are given all the necessary information, and then it is determined which ones used the information in the solution adopted in the general discussion;

3)the "cost" (value in terms of content) of the requested information is compared both qualitatively and quantitatively, depending on the value of the solution adopted. The information "price" is agreed first and the solution is assessed collectively by the students.

Thus, students learn to collect rational and goal-oriented information.

In the process of working with the situation, the reader, after familiarizing himself with the statement of the problem, independently analyzes the situation, diagnoses the problem and, in the process of discussion, together with other

readers, presents his ideas and solutions. If acquaintance with keys is carried out directly during the lesson, then for individual analysis, 10-30 minutes are usually allocated, depending on the size of the material. During the analysis, students learn to act in a "team", to adopt a multi-aspect analysis and solution. In most cases, a study time of 30 minutes to 2 hours is required to review the situation.

The duration of training depends on the complexity of the poured situation and how deeply the students have knowledge.

"Boomerang" technology provides an opportunity for the formation of critical thinking, logic; develops memory, ideas, thoughts, skills to state evidence in written and oral forms.

The method of "Boomerang" technology allows, along with education, to carry out a number of tasks of an educational nature: skills of working with a team, attitude, kindness, skillfulness, respect for other opinion, activity, the formation of leadership qualities, a creative approach to work, interest in the effectiveness of their activities, unbiased self-assessment, etc.

The method of "Boomerang" technology is aimed at learning, creative understanding, free possession of educational material in a deep and holistic state during one session.

The main concepts related to the method of "Boomerang" technology are as follows:

Open-ended questions-these questions allow you to continue dealing, speaking. They cannot be answered short, uniformly.

Closed questions-these questions presuppose the issuance of correct, open answers of the type "yes" or "no" in advance

Cross-examination is a series of short questions grouped together, which is a great opportunity to look for specific information and determine the position of arguments, opponents and make certain decisions.

Another of the interactive techniques is the problem technology method. We give an example of the use of problem Technology in training sessions.

The course is divided into two subgroups of students in the classroom. The table presented in this form is submitted to small groups. In this case, the first part of the table is written the question and the type of problem. The members of the small group each take the problem seriously and write their thoughts on the remaining empty two parts of the table.

The example of filling out the table by readers can be as follows:

Problem type	Come to the problem reason for the exit	Troubleshooting measures and your action
We say that the motherland is as sacred as sajdagah, but why do some people betray the motherland.	To enter the path of some ill-wishers due to their lack of independent opinion. Not reading books and without adult supervision stay, lack of cooperation in upbringing, the appearance of a gap in upbringing, the fact that a person does not use his mind, trustworthiness and that's it vs. not to use, trustworthiness and that's it others attendance.	Cooperation in education, work on oneself independently, read more books, spiritual and educational participate in events, follow an adult sentence, conduct various conversations. My action in this regard, follow the agenda to spend my time meaningfully doing it and to encourage those around you to do it, who reads a lot of books holding named contests and not to use, trustworthiness and that's it others attendance.

Problem type	Come to the problem reason for the exit	Troubleshooting measures and your action
Homeland-like sajdagah we say Holy, but why some people The motherland is cunning.		

In conclusion, the use of educational tools based on information and Communication Technologies is one of the requirements of today in order to further activate the teaching of "upbringing", provide additional educational materials to students, increase their interests, introduce various forms of assessment of their acquired knowledge. The educational site and mobile application created on the subject of "upbringing" can be used in the course of classes and in the organization of extracurricular activities. Such modern information education resources provide information resources based on multimedia technologies in addition to the textbook on the subject "upbringing" to students of the general secondary education school. The recommended e-learning resources include visual materials, fairy tales for elementary school students, stories and narratives, test tasks designed to assess the knowledge gained, strengthening students' knowledge.

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